

A PBL Approach Design for Fostering Female Vocations in IT Engineering

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Abstract

The underrepresentation of women in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) careers, is a global and national challenge. Although progress has been observed in the participation of women in STEM in Colombia, the relative gender gap, especially in Information Technologies (IT), remains significant and concerning. The department of Boyacá is not exempt from this reality, although the scarcity of specific data limits a detailed understanding of the local situation. This work addresses this issue by using student-centered approaches. It proposes the design of a Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach, mediated by a digital tool, aimed at female vocational high school students in Boyacá. The study seeks to identify some underlying causes for the low choice of IT careers among this specific group and in this context, to design, develop, and evaluate a contextualized educational intervention. A mixed-methodology approach will be employed, integrating qualitative and quantitative methods to explore causes and utilizing Design-Based Research (DBR) to design, construct, and evaluate the proposed approach. This research is expected to provide a validated intervention model and a deeper understanding of the factors influencing young women's educational and professional trajectories in a local context, thus contributing to efforts for gender equity in the technological field.

Keywords: Gender Gap; IT Engineering Education; Project-Based Learning

1 Introduction

The participation of women in the fields of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) has been a subject of global study. International data show that women represent approximately one-third of the research community (UNESCO, 2021) and close to 35% of students enrolled in higher education in STEM areas (UN Women, 2022; UNESCO, 2017). These differences in representation have historical backgrounds related to women's participation in scientific and academic institutions (Tonn, 2020).

In Colombia, data analysis between 2001 and 2021 indicates an increase in the absolute number of women graduating from STEM programs. However, their proportional representation relative to men has remained around an average of 37.9% during that period (Laboratorio de Economía de la Educación [LEE], 2023). Disaggregating by STEM areas¹⁰, the data for 2021 show significant variations: while women constitute the majority in the Sciences (56.3%), their participation decreases in Engineering (37.8%), Mathematics (34%), and finally Technology, where they represented only 20.3% of graduates. This field not only presents the lowest female participation but is also the only STEM area where the gender gap has widened over the last two decades (LEE, 2023). Both globally and in Colombia, female participation in Technology tends to be lower than the overall STEM average. The data point of 20.3% participation in Technology in Colombia is the lowest among the STEM areas analyzed in the LEE report and, according to the same report, represents a gap that has

¹⁰ The STEM categories, as defined in the source report are grouped as follows: **Sciences:** biology, physics, astronomy, geology, chemistry, and related fields (excluding health sciences). **Technology:** systems and computer engineering, software engineering, information and communication technologies engineering, informatics engineering, information systems management, and related fields. **Engineering:** engineering programs not included in the technology category, such as electrical, environmental, industrial, and civil engineering, among others. **Mathematics:** professional training programs in mathematics and statistics.

widened. This observation motivates a research focus centered on Engineering related to Information Technologies (IT).

This study focuses on the department of Boyacá, Colombia. Although the relevance of the topic at the regional level is recognized, there is limited availability of specific and disaggregated gender data on female participation in STEM and Technology within this context. This lack of detailed information hinders a deep understanding of the local situation. Nevertheless, Boyacá has implemented initiatives promoting digital inclusion and equity, such as the "Ella hace historia" program –in English, this expression could be translated as 'She makes history'– (Gobernación de Boyacá, 2021), business alliances for gender equity (Holcim Colombia, 2021), and investment in infrastructure like STEM laboratories (Secretaría de Educación de Boyacá, 2022). This panorama suggests a potentially receptive environment for focused interventions, but one that requires contextualized research to guide their design.

The reasons for investigating this topic are multifaceted. These align with principles of social justice and gender equity, as promoted by the UN Sustainable Development Goal 5 (Naciones Unidas, n.d.). Historical disparities in high-level scientific recognition (Nobel Prize Outreach AB, 2024) can also be interpreted as a reflection of systemic inequities that need to be addressed. From an economic and social perspective, it is argued that greater diversity in Technology could foster innovation. Furthermore, data for Colombia suggest that careers in engineering and technology tend to offer higher salaries and better employability rates compared to other fields (Navarro, 2022). Therefore, increased female participation in IT could contribute to reducing the overall gender pay gap (Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística [DANE], 2020). Additionally, with a projected deficit of engineers in the country (Navarro, 2022), fostering female talent becomes a dimension of national need. Finally, this research relates to national Science, Technology, and Innovation policies (Mission-Oriented Policy - POM), particularly the missions "Knowledge and innovation for equity" and "Educating with Quality". Estimates such as those from the World Economic Forum on the time needed to close the gender gap in Latin America (World Economic Forum [WEF], 2022) suggest the relevance of investigating and implementing focused interventions.

Given this situation, the main objective of the present work is to design, develop, and evaluate an educational strategy to explore factors related to the choice of IT Engineering careers and foster female vocational education for K-9 to K-11 students, through an open extracurricular intervention.

2 Associated Factors in STEM Career Choices: A Literature Review

The literature suggests that female representation in some fields may be influenced by a complex network of interrelated factors operating at different levels (Amozurrutia, 2012). Therefore, adopting a perspective that integrates sociocultural, psychological, and systemic dimensions is considered a relevant approach.

2.1 Sociocultural Factors

Studies indicate that from an early age, young women may be exposed to gender stereotypes that associate STEM careers, especially technological ones, with male domains (Catucci, n.d.; Louten, 2022). These stereotypes can be influenced by historical narratives (Tonn, 2020), media representations, and differentiated social expectations (Sociology Institute, 2022). PISA report data suggest that, at age 15, boys show a greater propensity to aspire to careers in science or engineering compared to girls, despite girls, in some cases, achieving better results in logic and mathematics tests (OECD, 2015).

2.2 Psychological Factors

The literature suggests a connection between sociocultural and psychological factors. Exposure to stereotypes could influence young women's self-efficacy and confidence in their abilities in STEM areas, even when their academic performance is comparable to that of their male peers (OECD, 2015). In academic and professional environments with a male predominance, some women might experience a lower sense of belonging, a factor that has been correlated with academic success and persistence (Beach et al., 2024). Self-Determination Theory (SDT) highlights the importance of satisfying the psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness to foster intrinsic motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2000), which is relevant for perseverance in fields like STEM. The perception of engineering as a field focused on "objects" rather than "people" has also been proposed as a possible deterrent for young women with a stronger social orientation (Baron-Cohen, 2009).

2.3 Systemic and Internalized Factors

Biases can also be present in automated systems, as illustrated by the case of Amazon's AI-based recruiting tool, which showed biases against female candidates due to the historical data used for its training (Dastin, 2018). This underlines the importance of considering ethical and inclusion aspects in the development of digital tools. Additionally, some studies explore the concept of internalized sexism, where individuals may adopt or perpetuate discriminatory attitudes (Association for Women in Science [AWIS], 2024; Schwabe, 2024).

These different types of factors appear to interact. Social stereotypes (Catucci, n.d.) could be related to psychological barriers such as a lack of confidence (OECD, 2015) or belonging (Beach et al., 2024). These barriers could be affected by biased systems (Dastin, 2018) or environments perceived as hostile, and over time, could be internalized (AWIS, 2024; Schwabe, 2024). Therefore, an intervention could benefit from considering these interconnections.

3 Research Approach

This study is guided by the following research questions:

RQ1: What are the factors associated with the choice of IT Engineering programs by female vocational high school students in Boyacá?

RQ2: How could digital tools be used to encourage female participation in IT Engineering programs?

RQ3: How can a project-based learning approach mediated by digital tools, oriented towards gender equity in the choice of IT Engineering programs in Boyacá, be designed?

To answer these questions, the project's overall objective is: To design a project-based learning approach mediated by digital tools as an instrument to promote gender equity in the choice of IT Engineering programs in Boyacá. This is broken down into three specific objectives:

Goal 1: To identify factors associated with female underrepresentation in IT Engineering programs that can be addressed from a project-based learning approach.

Goal 2: To design a project-based learning approach adapted to the identified scenario.

Goal 3: To evaluate the impact of the proposed PBL approach.

To achieve these objectives, the methodological framework chosen is Design-Based Research (DBR). This methodology is considered suitable due to its focus on solving educational problems in real contexts through iterative cycles of design, implementation, analysis, and redesign. DBR seeks to develop practical solutions (in this case, a digital PBL intervention) and simultaneously generate theoretical knowledge about the learning

principles that influence the intervention's effectiveness. As an educational approach, this research explores Project-Based Learning (PBL) as the core strategy, mediated by digital tools.

The execution of the DBR methodology will align with the specific objectives through the following phases:

- **Phases 1 and 2 (Problem Identification and Investigation - Corresponds to Goal 1):** This includes a literature review, characterization of the target population, and qualitative fieldwork (e.g., interviews, focus groups) to identify and categorize contextual factors and barriers in Boyacá, and those addressable through the PBL intervention will be selected.
- **Phases 3, 4, and 5 (Solution Development and Prototype Construction - Corresponds to Goal 2):** In this phase, the PBL pedagogical strategy will be defined, and a prototype of the mediating digital tool will be constructed.
- **Phase 6 (Application and Evaluation - Corresponds to Goal 3):** A pilot course will be carried out using the designed strategies and tools. The impact will be evaluated using a protocol that incorporates both quantitative and qualitative instruments to measure variables such as interest in IT, perceived self-efficacy, and attitudes.
- **Phase 7 (Redesign - Continuous Refinement):** The findings from the evaluation will inform adjustments to the approach, following the iterative nature of DBR.

The research starts with the assumption that the factors influencing Technology Careers choice vary by context, and that a subset of these factors (related to perceptions, self-efficacy, etc.) can be positively influenced by a digitally mediated PBL approach adapted to the local context.

4 Proposed Intervention and Expected Contributions

The central intervention of this research is the design and evaluation of a Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach mediated by digital tools. PBL is selected for its potential to increase motivation and interest by connecting learning with real-world problems (Archer, 2024). Special attention will be given to incorporating findings about local factors (as per Goal 1) and applying ethical principles to avoid biases, considering historical cases like the one documented by Dastin (2018). The approach will be directed at addressing the identified intervenable factors. For example, if stereotypes or a lack of role models emerge as barriers, the projects could be designed to showcase women in technology and highlight collaborative and social impact aspects.

Contributions are expected in several areas:

- **Theoretical:** Contributing to the contextualized understanding of the factors influencing career decisions in a local context, and to the literature on DBR and digitally mediated PBL with a gender equity focus.
- **Practical:** Generating an evidence-based and contextually adapted PBL intervention model, potentially useful for educational institutions in similar contexts, such as Sogamoso City and its surrounding area. This also includes providing a practical tool for educators and contributing more broadly to national (POM) and international (SDG 5) objectives.

This proposal seeks to integrate DBR and PBL in an iterative and adaptive manner, using active learning and employing technology strategically and ethically. This serves as an alternative to previous approaches that have sometimes been described in the literature as sporadic or decontextualized (Sociology Institute, 2022; OECD, 2015).

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